

Redesign of circular products: an analysis of the fashion industry

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Abstract. The concept of circular economy aims to extend the end-of-life of products by reducing or reusing products and materials, being Design a central part of a successful circular product. In line with the 6Rs strategy for circularity, Redesign (applied by eco-design practices) allows the creation of products that can be easily repaired, upgraded, or disassembled, extending their life, and fomenting a circular economy. For that reason, the aim of this research is to analyse the role of Redesign in the circularity of products. Exploratory qualitative research was conducted, with five in-depth interviews with founders and R&D managers of prominent footwear organizations. Results demonstrate that most interviewed companies, which were born circular, considered Redesign practices from the definition of the product concept. In conclusion, looking at Redesign strategies holistically and through its specific sub-relationships have a major impact on the company's circularity practises.

Keywords: Redesign, Circular Economy, R-strategies, Fashion Industry, Footwear industry

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1 Introduction

The linear economy is a take-make-waste model in which goods are manufactured from raw materials, sold, used, and then discarded as waste or incinerated when those products reach the end of their life [1]. As pointed by Huysman et al. [2] "a linear economy approach results in many environmental challenges: resources become depleted and end up as waste and emissions". The Circular Economy (CE) is an alternative to the linear economy, as it presents strategies to extend the end-of-life of a certain product with the reduction, reuse or refurbishment of materials in production/distribution and consumption processes [3]. In a CE model, products are designed for longevity and durability and, when they reach the end of their life, they are mostly used as inputs for a new product. One of the implementation strategies for circular products is the 6R model - reduce, reuse, recycle, recover, remanufacture, redesign – that focus on different phases of the product life cycle, being important strategies to implement a more sustainable manufacturing [4]. Here the Redesign phase is responsible for defining the main requirements of the product at the beginning of its life cycle, thus exerting a strong influence on all R-strategies and subsequent phases of the product development [5,6,7].

Many authors have explored the concept of CE in order to: reach a clear and embracing definition [3,8] and describe the different R-strategies and their implications [9,10,11]. A high proportion of the literature was found to address the end-of-life phases, namely the recycling and repairing processes, suggesting that the other phases are currently neglected [3,10]. From this context emerges the following research question: *what is the role of the Redesign phase for the product circularity?* To address this gap, this article aims to analyse the role of Redesign in the circularity of products.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: after this Introduction, section 2 elaborates on CE and R-strategies, and section 3 presents our adopted framework for redesign. In section 4, we present the research method, and then in section 5 we discuss the main results. Finally, in section 6 we present the conclusions and some future research directions.

2 Circular Economy and R-Strategies

The main aim of CE is to reconcile two seemingly opposing paradigms: sustained economic growth and effective protection of the environment and natural resources [12,13]. Its implementation is often achieved through different R-strategies [3], such as the 6Rs framework [4,7,10,11,14], which is defined by: **reduce** refers to the use of materials that generate less waste and thus use less substances, materials, product components, or entire products; **reuse** refers to a product that has already been used can be used again in its original function; **remanufacture** refers to a create a new product using (parts of) that old product with the same function; **recycle** means using different types of waste as a resource; **recover** involves the incineration of materials for energy generation; and **redesign** refers to the definition of requirements of a product at the beginning of its life cycle. Summing up, although with different approaches, the

implementation of each R-strategy requires a certain adjustment in product's design, thus the relevance of the Redesign strategy to the CE.

2.1 The Contribution of Redesign to Circular Economy

The Redesign strategy acknowledges that the design of a product can influence a product's durability, lifespan and its potential for end-of-life reuse or recycling [15,16]. Redesign has two main objectives: the first aims to identify the problems that the original product represents in terms of its functionality and effects on the environment; the second is to tweak the most important components to produce an upgraded version of the original product, resulting that strikes an effective balance between usefulness and environmental benefits [17]. Summing up, Redesign stands at the beginning of the product life cycle, influencing all the R-strategies that support product circularity [16]. The implementation of the Redesign strategy can be done through eco-design (also known as sustainable design), that serve as the basis for designing products for CE [6]. The product development process must be shaped by eco-design principles prior to the product's manufacturing, starting by understanding the problem and the customer's needs, exploring possible solutions to that problem, including prototyping, and selecting the best solution [18]. However, the development of eco-design practices poses several challenges for companies. The main one is that all decisions in this process should be made by an interdisciplinary team including designers, project managers, manufacturing engineers, value chain managers and sustainability experts [14,19]. For instance, the need to Redesign products and processes will require a close collaboration with supply chain partners in order to combine knowledge and promote innovation in the Redesign phase [7]. For that reason, we propose a framework that describes how Redesign strategies can be incorporated through the different phases of the product life cycle from manufacture to disposal.

3 Framework for Redesign

The product circularity has emerged as a crucial aspect of sustainability, as it involves designing of products that can be recycled, repaired, or reused at the end of their life cycle [20]. Implementing Redesign practices poses several challenges for companies, especially at the product development stage [21]. For that reason, it is necessary to define which Redesign strategies can be implemented at the different stages of the product life cycle, including aspects related to circularity strategies.

A review of different frameworks and design implementation strategies towards circularity and sustainability was conducted [14,16,18,22], aiming to discuss the relationship between the application of different Redesign strategies by the departments of an organization, providing an overview of the full product development process. This review is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Review

Organizational Level	Redesign Strategy	Characteristics
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Designers	Product concept development	Reuse: Optimization of product; Maximize technical life of the product & components. Remanufacture: integration of functions.
Manufacturing / Value Chain experts	Optimization of production techniques	Reduce: Minimize use of resources in production and transportation. Reuse: easy maintenance; durability.
	Optimization of Distribution system	
	Optimization of product lifetime	
Sustainability Experts	Selection of low-impact materials	Reduce: Maximize availability of resources.
	Optimization of the end-of-life	Remanufacture: Facilitate upgrading Recycle: Recyclability of components.

As outlined in Table 1, each organizational department is considered responsible for many design goals and corresponding design strategies that have been identified as design for environment strategies [16]. The design department is responsible for developing the product concept and thus optimizing the product itself as well as integrating functions. Manufacturing and Value Chain experts play a central role in optimizing production techniques, the distribution system, and the life cycle of a product. As a result, many strategies can be implemented (e.g., use of clean energy, energy-efficient logistics, product longevity). Sustainability experts are responsible for selecting environmentally friendly materials and optimizing end-of-life. This can be achieved through renewable energy selection, evaluation of sourcing options, remanufacturing, and reuse of products. The application of this framework to an existing business will provide a deeper understanding of the role each department plays in the Redesign strategy for manufacturing and the life cycle of a circular product.

In conclusion, Table 1 encompasses different Redesign strategies, its circular impact and its relation to the different organizational levels of an organization. As next steps, it will be used as guidelines for empirical research in organizations that are implementing circular strategies, thus demonstrating how each organizational level and influence the implementation of Redesign strategies, also emphasizing the involvement of other actors into collaborative networks of circularity.

4 Research Method

The Redesign of a product is a crucial aspect of the product life cycle, as it involves changing the design of a product to make it more sustainable, durable and resource efficient, thereby reducing waste and minimizing the environmental impact of the product throughout its life cycle [16]. To achieve the research objectives, we conducted qualitative exploratory research to analyse the subjective perspectives of individuals or groups in relation to a new or developing phenomenon [23]. Data was collected with representatives from different organizations, using semi-structured interviews [24]. The aim was to interview different types of companies in the fashion industry that are committed to sustainable practises. In this way, we were able to gather relevant knowledge about the complexities, challenges and existing needs of implementing sustainable practises in a company. Table 2 summarizes the interviewees profile:

Table 2. Interviewed companies and representative's profile.

#	Sector	Employees	Representative's profile	Time at the company
A	Fashion accessories and footwear retail	<25	Founder, Creative Director	15 years
B	Apparel & footwear retail	<25	Head of Product Development	12 years
C	Footwear research centre	n/a	Senior Researcher	18 years
D	Fashion accessories and footwear retail	<25	CEO and Design Director	6 years
E	Fashion footwear retail	+/- 150	Brand Manager	9 years

All interviews were transcribed and analysed through a content analysis approach [25], which were complemented with other documents and papers about the sector.

5 Results

The fashion industry is a complex ecosystem that, in general, has a negative environmental impact, poor labour practices and relevant waste generation [25]. However, interviews show that many companies are changing this behaviour towards more sustainable practices. Technology is playing a central role in changing practices in the industry - from advanced materials to innovative manufacturing processes – impacting design, production and even recycling. As mentioned by Interviewee A, by using cutting-edge materials such as sustainable plastics and bio-based components, designers and entrepreneurs are redefining the boundaries of sustainable practices by reducing the negative footprint while maximizing innovation. The current landscape reflects a growing emphasis on the circular economy, what requires collaboration between different departments of an organization through the different steps of the product life cycle.

Regarding **product concept development**, results demonstrated the importance of Redesign to optimize the circularity approach from the beginning of product concept. Setting clear sustainability goals at the concept stage ensures that all subsequent design and production decisions are in line with these goals. This proactive approach is likely to lead to better results than integrating sustainability into an existing product. In addition, it is important to design objects that are not only for immediate consumption, but also have a timeless aesthetic that ensures they will still be relevant in years to come - balancing sustainability, aesthetics and consumer desires.

Regarding **optimization of production techniques**, results suggested that the fashion world is paying close attention to optimizing production techniques when it comes to achieving product circularity. This transition is in line with the core ideas of circular design, which emphasize resource efficiency and the reduction of material waste [6]. Interviewee C mentions that “3D printers, for example, allow greater design freedom, less material waste and intricate geometries that were previously unattainable, and that this could lead to a more efficient production process”. In addition, interviewee D mentions that “the company's current goal is to produce small quantities of products, avoiding mass production and aim for a just-in-time production system”.

Regarding **optimization of distribution system**, all interviewed companies are aware of the impact of emissions and pollution caused by the transport and distribution system and are constantly looking for ways to produce locally to minimize transport-related emissions. Solutions such as factories that prioritize sustainable transport practices, and technological advances to optimize distribution and production, were also mentioned. Interviewee from company B adds that “on the one hand transport from Asian countries to Europe is not sustainable, but on the other it is the only option at the moment. The development and use of new materials in the industry will be key to reducing transport emissions by sourcing locally”.

Regarding **optimization of product lifetime**, longevity is a cornerstone of Redesign in the fashion industry. Being often driven by fleeting trends, the emphasis on products that stand the test of time is a significant innovation. On the other hand, interviewee E mentions that “in order to have a more durable product, sometimes we rely on processes and materials that are not the most sustainable”. This gives an interesting insight into how holistically each strategy needs to be considered and the impact this can have on the price of the final product.

Regarding the **selection of low-impact materials**, there is common shift towards environmentally friendly materials and maximizing material benefits. The use of organic fibres, biodegradable materials, or using material waste for smaller accessories, illustrates the circular principle of minimizing waste and optimizing resource use. Interviewee from company A mentioned that “we identified a bio-material, much more sustainable. However, the carbon footprint to bring this material from Asia would have a bigger impact than the circularity of the material itself. That lead us to give up on this material for now”. Interviewee C complements “The materials in a product should represent between 60 and 80 per cent of the product's footprint. In other words, the selection of materials is fundamental to reducing the environmental footprint of products”.

Regarding the **optimization of the end-of-life**, there is an effort of interviewed companies to optimize the end of life in a series of practices such as: design that allow an easy disassembly of product; reusing and recycling materials from old products; integration of unsold or unused products into a platform for resale; buy-back programs; disassembling shoes and reusing components for new products or recycling materials; easy replacement and repair of components. On the other hand, interviewee D points out the challenges of implementing repair and circular economy for brands due to logistical barriers, trust issues and the need for efficient processes, especially for global brands.

Summing up, these examples illustrate a move away from the linear "take-produce-dispose" model and demonstrate the industry's commitment to Redesign their products for waste reduction and sustainable product lifecycles. As fashion brands embrace repair, remanufacturing and recycling as integral parts of their business, the contours of the circular economy are taking shape in the industry.

6 Conclusion

Given the main characteristics of the fashion industry – short seasonality, mass production and consumption, luxury and accessory item, the adoption of circular

strategies is still a challenge. In this context, the objective of this article - to analyse the role of Redesign in the circularity of products – lead to relevant insights and a deeper reflection about the sustainability of the “fashion business model”.

Most interviewed organizations were born circular, what means they applied Redesign strategies not only at product level, but at Business Model level. In that sense, the application of Redesign strategies throughout the different organization levels and product life cycle shed light on the debate about the misalignment between the current fashion industry and the concepts of circularity, sustainability, and value chain resilience. The effort to produce and consume local allows the application of a broader number of circular strategies, while relying on external providers (such as Asian suppliers and producers) might hinder the achievement of circularity goals.

In conclusion, the application of Redesign strategies at different organizational levels allowed a holistic view of how these strategies are closely linked. The proposed framework, which guided the results presented, demonstrated a broader view of how Redesign practises were implemented by different companies in the fashion industry. In particular, it highlighted the importance of looking at design strategies holistically and considering the specific sub-relationships that exist between them, leading to a broader impact on the company's sustainable practises. Redesign influences most stages of product life-cycle and should be considered right at product concept definition. Another insight that emerged is the so-called emotional design, which emphasises the importance of the concept of user-centred design.

Given the limited profile of companies in the Fashion Industry, we suggest for future studies to expand the sample and the analysis not only to other cases but also other sectors. The transformation of companies to circular products are based on redesign, so the discussion of this topic in different sectors might bring relevant guidelines and recommendations.

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